

User Guide: LSTPM Cooling Effect Analysis Tool

Version: 1.0 **Date:** December 2025 **Applicable OS:** Microsoft Windows 10/11

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1. Overview

The **LSTPM Analysis Tool** is a standalone software designed to implement the *Land Surface Temperature Parameterization Method (LSTPM)* proposed in the associated manuscript (Figure 1). It allows researchers, urban planners, and ecologists to automatically quantify the cooling effects of urban Blue-Green Spaces (BGS) without requiring programming skills or specialized remote sensing software.

Key Features:

- **Automated Calculation:** Computes Cooling Intensity (CI), Distance (CD), Efficiency (CE), and Gradient (CG).
- **Physical Visualization:** Generates "Gradient Flow" maps visualizing the heat exchange process.
- **Auto-Correction:** Automatically handles Coordinate Reference System (CRS) mismatches between vector and raster data.

Figure 1. Interface of the LSTPM Analysis Tool

2. Data Requirements

Before running the tool, please prepare the following two input files:

1. BGS Vector Data (.shp)

- **Format:** ESRI Shapefile (must include .shp, .shx, .dbf, .prj files).
- **Content:** Polygon features representing the boundaries of parks, water bodies, or green spaces.
- **Coordinate System:** Projected Coordinate System (PCS) is recommended (e.g., UTM) for accurate distance calculation. *Note: The tool will automatically reproject this to match the LST image if they differ.*

2. Land Surface Temperature Raster (.tif)

- **Format:** GeoTIFF (.tif).
 - **Content:** A single-band raster representing Land Surface Temperature (LST).
 - **Unit:** Degrees Celsius (°C) is recommended for interpretable CI results.
 - **Resolution:** Matches the source data (e.g., 30m for Landsat 8).
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3. Step-by-Step Instructions

Step 1: Launch the Application

Double-click **LSTPM_Tool.exe** to start the program. No installation is required. (*Note: It may take 10–20 seconds to load upon the first launch.*)

Step 2: Select Input Data

1. **BGS Vector (.shp):** Click the "**Browse...**" button and select your shapefile containing the park polygons.
2. **LST Raster (.tif):** Click the "**Browse...**" button and select your LST GeoTIFF file.

Step 3: Select Output Directory

Click "**Browse...**" to select a folder where the results (Excel tables, shapefiles, and plots) will be saved.

Step 4: Run Analysis

Click the green "**Start Analysis**" button.

- The **Process Log** at the bottom will display real-time progress (e.g., "*Processing feature 5/100...*").
- *Please wait patiently.* Processing time depends on the number of parks and the size of the raster image.

Step 5: Completion

When the log shows >>> All tasks completed successfully!, a pop-up window will confirm the completion. You may now close the tool and check the output folder.

4. Interpretation of Outputs

The tool generates three types of files in your selected output directory:

1. Indicators Table (LSTPM_Results.xlsx)

A spreadsheet containing the calculated indicators for each park:

- **ID:** The index of the park feature.
- **CI (Cooling Intensity):** Temperature difference between the park boundary and the cooling limit (°C).
- **CD (Cooling Distance):** The maximum range of the cooling effect (meters).
- **CE (Cooling Efficiency):** The ratio of the cooling area to the park area (dimensionless).
- **CG (Cooling Gradient):** The rate of temperature change (°C/m).
- **Success:** 1 indicates a valid cooling effect was identified; 0 indicates no significant cooling effect was found.

2. Cooling Extent Map (LSTPM_Cooling_Extents.shp)

A vector file showing the specific spatial footprint of the cooling effect.

- **Blue Polygons:** These represent the area where the BGS exerts a dominant cooling influence, determined by the LSTPM algorithm.
- You can drag this file into ArcGIS/QGIS to overlay with urban maps.

3. Visualization Plots (Folder: LSTPM_Plots/)

This folder contains JPG images for each successfully identified park (e.g., Park_0_Flow.jpg).

- **Background:** LST distribution (Red = Hot, Blue = Cool).
 - **Red Line:** The original boundary of the BGS.
 - **Blue Area:** The identified physical cooling extent.
 - **Black Arrows: Gradient Flow Vectors.** These arrows indicate the direction of heat flow. In a valid cooling area, arrows generally point from the hotter surroundings towards the cooler park (Centripetal Gradient).
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5. Troubleshooting

- **Result contains all zeros:**
 - Ensure your SHP and TIF geographically overlap.
 - Ensure the TIF file does not contain NoData values (e.g., -999) inside the park area.
- **Program freezes:**
 - For large datasets, the tool may appear unresponsive while processing.